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HEALTHCARE PRACTICE STANDARDS FOR PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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ABSTRACT

The ever increasing development of our society has facilitated significant progress in nursing profession. Healthcare practice for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction requires that professional medical nurses be constantly focused on various aspects of patients' condition. The major impact factors that define the specifics of the nursing care practice for these patients have proved to be providing of state-of-the-art effective care services to enable the patients' constant observation, assessment of the patients' special needs and healthcare planning based on the coronary syndrome progression. Delivery of high standards in healthcare practice in patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction is seen impracticable unless new methodology and approaches are introduced as to implementation of the nursing process concept and elaboration of a nursing care plan based on the individual patient's needs.

Keywords: healthcare, acute myocardial infarction, patients.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare services have proved of significant importance for the entire process of patients' therapy. The healthcare standards tend to contribute to a considerable extent to a stable economy and a sustainable development of medical institutions. The practice standards serve as the fundamental method of assessment of the healthcare services. Also, these may be instrumental to comparability of the clinical outcomes and unified criteria and approaches to prevent further complications. The correct standard apprehension tends to ensure ever higher quality healthcare standards for the benefit of better efficiency, respectively. This may require an analysis of the needs of patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, introduction of entirely new approach to services provided by healthcare professionals

in state-of-the-art clinics, lifetime enhancement of qualifications to full satisfaction of the needs of healthcare industry.

For the purposes of improvement of the healthcare practice standards in delivery of services to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, the medical nurse education assigns to medical nurses a new role to play and assumption of duties and responsibilities demanding specific knowledge to be acquired throughout continuing training and certifications. Every nurse in the present days must be the face which with his/her knowledge and competency shall address the ever increasing healthcare needs of population.

OBJECT

This research is aimed at analyzing the nurses' opinions with respect to the healthcare issues, services

and practice standards for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction.

RESOURCES AND METHODOLOGY

This research extends to medical nurses operating in the departments of cardiology in three multi-disciplinary hospitals across the North-Western Bulgaria as to Multi-Disciplinary Hospital of Active Treatment “Christo Botev” of Vratsa, Multi-Disciplinary Hospital of Active Treatment “Stamen Iliev” of Montana and Multi-Disciplinary Hospital of Active Treatment “Saint Petka” of Vidin. As many as 150 medical nurses have been inquired by the tool of direct anonymous survey. The survey data has been processed by means of the SPSS v.19 statistical computer programme featuring qualitative and quantitative parameters for identification of pending issues.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The healthcare practice standards in patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction proves to be in direct interdependence with the present day professional training of medical nurses. Pursuing of a policy

and implementation of measures with respect to the healthcare practice standards in modern times involves continual improvement and expansion of objectives and activities of the organization and its personnel training. The medical nurses training is aiming to intensively provide information of the proper result evaluation, extension of aid and support to patients, carrying novelty into practice in compliance with the ethical and professional standards.

For the benefit of improvement of the healthcare practice standards in the medical institutions, it becomes necessary for the medical nurses to have adequate training in order to meet our society needs and to avail themselves of alternatives to their professional careers.

Most of the nursing personnel (75,6%) admit the need of conducting a special profile training in providing healthcare services for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction. Whereas for 34,5%, it is a case of absolute necessity, for 24,1%, it is necessary, while for 17,0%, it is occasionally required. According to 24,4% of them, special profile training for medical nurses proves of little avail, while assumptions as to there is no need are never checked (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Necessity of special profile training of medical nurses in providing healthcare services to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction

For the purposes of improvement of the nursing healthcare practice standards in various medical institutions, a multitude of methodology and tools, meeting the local rules and regulations, have been implemented with respect to the medical services delivered to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction.

The nursing process, the nurses' diagnoses and the nursing healthcare plan are considered an entirely new approach in the medical nurses' training. The nursing process represents a significant part of the nursing practice and is considered a key factor for enhancement of healthcare practice standards in providing services to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction. We therefore have come up with a decision to examine the levels of knowledge of medical nurses of the nursing

process. Out of 44,5% of the medical nurses involved in the survey report a thorough knowledge of the nursing process, whereas 48,6% are only partially familiar with it, while at least 6,9% declare no knowledge of the nursing process. In view of the various obstacles, and first and foremost, the lack of unified standardized nursing record system in our country, we have posed a question to the medical nurses, as follows: “Does the Nursing Process apply in Your clinic?” “Some 25,6% of the medical nurses inquired report that the Nursing Process has been implemented in their medical institution. Whereas as much as 54,2% report that separate stages of it are only put into practice, 20,2% contend it has never been applied (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Opinion of medical nurses of putting into practice of the Nursing Process for patients suffering from Myocardial infarction

Nowadays the role of the medical nurse is related to the Nursing Process to ensure continual high standard and adequate professional healthcare services. 81,1% out of the medical nurses inquired of the criteria determining the needs of patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, point out to “the measured so-

matic indices”, some 13,9% of the medical professionals involved in the survey indicate that the criteria for assessment of the patients’ needs is defined “by 14th basic needs of Virginia Henderson”, while 3,0% define “at the request of the patient and his/her relatives” and 2,0% - “within my own discretion” (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Criteria to define the needs of patients of nursing cares

It is generally considered that the lack of medical nurses’ knowledge of the nature of the Nursing Process is a consequence of non-availability of a standing practice established in diagnostics from medical nurses in Bulgaria and a decision-making process of their own. The respond given by the patients is regarded an evidence of non-implementation of the Nursing Process. As much as 52,8% of them purport to be not satisfied, some 21,1% are not satisfied to the utmost. 26,1%, at the very least, claim to be satisfied.

The care plan is an integral part of the nursing process following the patient’s needs identification stage. Therein are laid down the short-, middle- and long-term objectives. The care plan incorporates the treatment, patient’s expectations, training and the medical nurses’

recommendations aimed at setting up modern and effective care arrangements to facilitate the medical nurses’ continual observation of the patient, assessment of the needs of special nursing care and the care planning according to the acute coronary syndrome progression. We therefore have posed a question, as follows: “Do you envisage working out care plans upon admitting patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction to Your clinic?” The respond to this question that prevails amongst the medical nurses inquired – 61,7% is defined as “Yes, we have such plans elaborated”, while for 33,5% of them it reads “There are occasional plans worked out” and at least 4,8% point out “No, there is no such plan in the making” (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Allocation of the medical nurses taking part in the healthcare plan elaboration

Evident from the survey outcome, the now established organization has only occasionally facilitated working out a nursing care plan for the patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction which is indicative of the need of a sweeping change of the organization to enable performance of care services as per a pre-meditated plan. Delivery of high standards healthcare practice for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction is not likely to succeed until new methodology and approaches of cares are introduced and implemented as to elaboration of a nursing care plan based on the individual patient’s needs.

According to most of the medical nurses – 61,4%, they fully meet the knowledge, skills and qualifications requirements. However, the medical nurse profession is closely related to its core activity progress which con-

sists in improvement of the healthcare practice standards. To the question “What do You think does turn to be conducive to the utmost extent to improvement of the healthcare practice standards in patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction?”, the general opinion of the medical nurses surveyed - 63,6% is “enhancement of the personnel qualifications”. Some 20,8% consider that “improvement of the work arrangements” shall translate into enhancement of the practice standards of the care services provided. At least 4,4% out of the surveyed have point out “the improvement of the general medical institution hygiene” as a method for higher healthcare practice standards. 11,2% of the personnel consider that “the improvement of the personnel attitude toward the patient” may turn fundamental to the enhancement of the healthcare practice standards (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Medical nurses’ opinion for enhancement of the healthcare practice standards

The opinion of more than half of the medical nurses (74,2%) is that there shall occur a change in attitude towards the patients during their hospitalization. They themselves would recommend a stronger patient commitment in observance of the hospital rules and regimen and stimulation of the patient co-operation in performing the prescribed therapy and providing nursing cares.

Healthcare services for patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction must meet the requirements arising out of or connected with the specifics and the

patient’s needs of care, on the one hand, and on the other, create conditions for the personnel to deliver high standards and effective care. The present day hospital services require specific medical technologies and high quality medical materials and supplies. However, better results are only feasible depending on the available services provided and the order of procedures involved in the entire medical and diagnostic process.

To contribute to higher healthcare practice standards in patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, the medical nurses must always strive to advance

the already acquired theoretical knowledge and practical skills by way of qualification enhancement. A considerable share takes the opinion of the medical nurses (92,5 %), according to which additional training courses to enhance the medical nurses' qualifications to deliver services to patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction should be set as a requirement.

Whereas as much as 76,7% of them consider it an absolute necessity, some 15,8% of the medical nurses regard additional training necessary to address specific issues, while the remaining 7,5% dismiss the need of supplementary training courses (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Requirements for continuing education courses for medical nurses

CONCLUSIONS:

Nursing profession is based on the basic human needs and necessities. However, advances in medical sciences add new dimensions. The nursing care services are conceived to enable medical nurses to deliver adequate cares for the patients while rendering an account of their general condition and medical examinations and prescribed therapy as planned by their attending physicians.

Hence the requirement to be satisfied by the medical nurses who must be able to perform not only their autonomous functions but also those arising out of or connected with medical doctors' prescribed therapy in line with the urgency, intensity and the patient's tolerance to invasive (or surgical) procedures and therapeutic treatment. Nowadays delivery of high healthcare practice standards in the cardiologic departments tends to be impracticable unless new care methodology and approaches are implemented as to elaboration of a nursing care plan based on the individual needs of patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction.

All things considered, the incorporation of new models and principles in the action of healthcare professionals and introduction of standards, rules and regulations to promote better cardiologic nursing practice have been acknowledged and confirmed in due course.

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